

Children's and parents' modal choice when commuting to primary school and air pollution burden: Is there a healthier way to commute?

Dominika Tóthová^{a*}, Ondřej Mikeš^b, Vilém Pařil^c, Petr Tonev^d

^a*Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^b*RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^c*Institute for Transport Economics, Geography and Policy, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

^d*Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic;*

*Dominika Tóthová, dominika.tothova@econ.muni.cz Department of Regional Economics, Faculty of Economics and Administration, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

Abstract

Urban transportation choices significantly influence personal air pollution exposure, especially for vulnerable populations such as children. This study investigates the determinants of parental decisions regarding children's school commuting modes and analyses the resulting differences in personal exposure to PM_{2.5}. Using questionnaire data (N = 267) and mobile monitoring of air pollution (10,309 observations from 151 children in Brno, Czech Republic), we applied multinomial logistic regression and mixed-effects models to examine how socio-economic characteristics, mobility preferences, and environmental awareness shape mode choice and air quality exposure. Results show that active and public transport modes are associated with higher PM_{2.5} exposure compared to car travel, particularly during winter. Families with higher environmental awareness are more likely to choose sustainable modes despite potentially higher exposure. Additionally, we examined alternative routes for walking, cycling, and scooter commuting, demonstrating that exposure can be partially reduced, supporting the potential benefits of targeted policy measures.

Keywords

Commuting, school, children, air quality, particulate matter, alternative routes

1. Introduction

The mode of transportation in urban areas can significantly influence air quality, with transport being a typical source of pollution in cities (Colville et al., 2001). The impact is particularly acute during morning peak hours, when many trips are taken as individuals commute to workplaces and children travel to schools. These concentrated emissions exacerbate urban air pollution levels and increase air pollution exposure for residents, particularly vulnerable population subgroups such as children, pregnant women or the elderly (Peled, 2011).

The mode of transportation children use to commute to school plays a fundamental role in shaping their physical, mental, and social well-being. Active commuting, such as walking or cycling, not only contributes to better cardiovascular health and reduced obesity risk but also supports sustainable urban mobility by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution (Davison et al., 2008; Larouche et al., 2014; J. R. Panter et al., 2010). However, these benefits are not guaranteed. In areas with poor air quality or unsafe infrastructure, active commuting can paradoxically expose children to environmental hazards such as traffic-related air pollution, especially near major roads, schools, and intersections (Połednik et al., 2023; Pratt et al., 2015; Targino et al., 2018). This dual nature of commuting underscores the importance of integrating health, environmental, and infrastructural considerations into school travel planning and urban design.

This study examines the factors influencing parental decisions regarding their children's mode of transport to school, focusing on socio-economic, preferential, and environmental determinants. It also investigates the extent of children's exposure to air pollution depending on their chosen transport mode. The analysis addresses whether active transportation options provide a healthier alternative in terms of lower exposure to traffic-related air pollution, while promoting physical activity and offering health benefits. This dual perspective contributes to a broader understanding of sustainable and health-conscious urban mobility.

Understanding these differences is essential for developing strategies that support safe, accessible, and health-promoting transport options, fostering a more equitable and sustainable approach to school commuting. At the same time, this research offers valuable insights into how urban transport systems can reduce long-term health risks and support healthy ageing, underlining the links between sustainable mobility, air quality, and population health throughout the life course. The findings thus contribute to the broader understanding of transport behaviour in one of the most sensitive contexts, children's school commuting, and its implications for their healthy development. Moreover, knowledge of how various transport modes influence exposure can inform not only child-focused policies but also strategies to mitigate health risks for older adults through better environmental planning.

There is a significant research gap concerning the relationship between the determinants of transport mode choice and the imbalance between the health benefits of sustainable commuting and the potential exposure to air pollution. While the health effects of physical activity and

transport-related externalities have been widely studied separately, the extent of this imbalance remains unclear. The primary objective of this study is to identify factors shaping children's school transport choices, including safety perceptions and socio-economic aspects, and to examine how these choices influence their exposure to air pollution, especially when more sustainable modes may paradoxically increase exposure to harmful pollutants.

Despite a growing body of international research, few studies focus specifically on primary school children and their unique commuting patterns. Furthermore, literature rarely examines how parental environmental awareness influences transport decisions. In the Czech context, studies often overlook these specific conditions or fail to reflect the cultural and infrastructural factors relevant to children's commuting. This research thus aims to address whether environmental awareness among parents leads to the choice of more sustainable transport modes while also considering the air pollution burden children may face during their daily commutes.

1.1 Children's mode choice for school commuting and air pollution exposure

Research into the determinants of children's school travel choices reveal a complex interplay of individual, environmental, and socio-economic factors that shape diverse commuting patterns depending on local context and economic status. A key determinant is the geographical distance between home and school. Shorter distances favour active commuting modes like walking or cycling, which align with both health and environmental goals, while longer distances necessitate motorised transport, driven by considerations of time, cost, and convenience (McDonald, 2007; Mitra & Buliung, 2012). Studies from various global contexts underscore spatial differences in commuting choices, noting that children from suburban areas facing longer distances are more likely to rely on cars. Meanwhile, children living in urban centres more frequently choose active commuting modes. Müller et al. (2008) confirm these findings by emphasising that distance, car availability, and weather are significant factors affecting school commuting decisions, indicating the multifaceted nature of such choices. Studies also focus on the built environment's impact on commuting choices. For instance, Ewing et al. (2004) found that children with shorter walking or cycling times and safe infrastructure are more likely to walk or cycle. Helbich (2017) explored urban form's influence in the Netherlands, noting that density and street layout can encourage active commuting by reducing distances and improving safety. Silvestri et al. (2022) indicate that commuters, more sensitive to negative transport externalities, tend to prefer private vehicles over public transport or active travel modes. This result points to a potential paradox in how these externalities are perceived.

Furthermore, parental safety concerns, including traffic, crime, and the availability of pedestrian or cycling infrastructure, heavily influence their commuting decisions, often pushing families toward motorised transport in areas lacking safe walking routes (Panter et al., 2011). Where parents perceive a lack of safety, car travel often becomes the preferred choice (Mitra & Buliung, 2012). Quality infrastructure, including sidewalks, bike lanes, and safe crossings, is essential for encouraging active commuting; without it, families prioritise convenience over

sustainability (Ewing et al., 2004; Helbich, 2017). Yeung et al. (2008) further support the role of distance and provide additional insights into parental decision-making, highlighting factors like safe paths, adult supervision, and the child's age as central considerations for promoting active commuting. For instance, in the Netherlands, factors such as urban density and street layout have been found to promote active commuting by reducing distances and improving route safety (Helbich, 2017). Parental constraints, including work schedules, frequently necessitate car use, as convenience often outweighs health or environmental considerations (Carver et al., 2013). On the other hand, school policies and community initiatives can significantly influence commuting choices. Schools that offer bus services or incentivise eco-friendly travel methods, such as providing bike storage, tend to promote higher rates of active commuting among students. Conversely, restrictions on parking or drop-off zones can reduce car use, further encouraging alternative commuting options (Bostock, 2001).

Moreover, socio-economic factors play a fundamental role in commuting choices. Families with higher incomes have greater flexibility due to access to cars, while lower-income families often depend on public transport, facing issues with convenience and safety (Jago et al., 2010). Social influences, such as peer norms, also play a role, encouraging active commuting when other children use similar modes (Jago et al., 2010). Additionally, rising environmental awareness influences family decisions, with some prioritising sustainable choices like walking or cycling to mitigate climate change and pollution concerns (Bernetti et al., 2008). Bernetti et al. (2008) showed that gender, age, employment, and vehicle availability are essential variables influencing the commuting choice. Disparities in socio-economic resources among families can contribute to an inequitable burden among children who commute actively versus those who rely on cars.

In contrast, passive commuting modes, such as using a car or public transport, are often chosen for their convenience or necessity, especially for families facing challenges like long distances, limited infrastructure, or safety concerns (Nelson et al., 2008; Pantelaki et al., 2024). Despite the benefits of active commuting, passive modes remain common, particularly in urbanised areas where safety and accessibility issues may deter walking or cycling (Marquart & Schicketanz, 2022). In addition, some research confirmed that individuals facing pollution risks increase their use of automobile commuting over active modes, particularly on polluted days (Fan et al., 2021).

Passive commuting, mainly using cars, significantly impacts urban air quality, posing health risks to those who walk or cycle near roadways. Studies reveal that pedestrians are exposed to hotspots of pollutants near traffic lights and public transport stops (Targino et al., 2018). Moreover, during peak hours, traffic-related particle concentrations are up to four times higher than off-peak times, exacerbating pedestrian exposure to particulate matter (Połednik et al., 2023). Seasonal factors, such as thermal inversions, further amplify pollutant levels, particularly in colder months, increasing the exposure of vulnerable road users (Ilenič et al., 2024). Car use in cities is a major source of air pollution that affects public health by causing respiratory and cardiovascular issues, particularly in vulnerable groups such as children and the elderly (Krzyzanowski et al., 2005). Long-term exposure to fine particulate matter and other

pollutants originating from traffic is associated with higher rates of asthma, allergies, and impaired lung function (Salvi, 2007). Studies show that children living in highly polluted areas are at increased risk of acute respiratory illnesses as well as long-term health issues, such as cognitive development disorders and a heightened risk of cardiovascular diseases in adulthood (Alvarez-Pedrerol et al., 2017a; Groner et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024) Exposure near schools and playgrounds, where children spend a significant portion of their day, is particularly concerning.

Together, these findings highlight a multifaceted array of factors, from physical distance and safety to social influences and environmental awareness, affecting school-aged children's commuting choices. While active commuting offers substantial health and psychological benefits, car commuting remains a necessary or preferred option for many families due to safety, distance, convenience, and socio-economic constraints. The disparity in commuting experiences underlines a potential burden gap between children who engage in active commuting and those who commute passively by car. Addressing these differences through improved policies and infrastructure could help create safer, accessible, and health-promoting commuting environments, ultimately supporting equitable health and environmental outcomes for all children. Existing research shows that more environmentally conscious commuters may prefer the safer and more convenient mode of transport by car. Particularly in the case of transporting primary school-age children, this tendency is highlighted concerning child safety. This incentive may be further reinforced by the distance of the school and commuting from a suburban area, as well as the representation of a certain family status reflected by the possibility of car use.

2. Data and methods

Understanding the factors that shape transportation choices for their children's school commutes requires a comprehensive approach integrating survey data and direct environmental exposure measurements. Our research focuses on mobile monitoring of air pollution exposure among the population of school-age children in Brno, Czech Republic. The study includes children from primary schools in the city of Brno. All primary schools, approximately 100 in total, were invited to participate. Schools joined the study based on interest, and within those schools, we introduced the research to students, who then voluntarily signed up for participation. The study involved children from all grade levels of primary school, ranging from 6 to 15 years old. These children took part in the air pollution exposure measurements, providing essential air pollution exposure data and time-activity diaries. Their parents participated in the questionnaire survey (original group), including mobility and spatio-temporal data, health and associated financial expenditure data, household data, attitudes, and demographic and socio-economic characteristics, which examined the factors influencing their transportation choices for school commutes. This selection process ensured voluntary participation while capturing a broad representation of school-aged children and their families.

Investigating the factors influencing parents' transportation choices for their children's school commutes requires an electronic questionnaire using the Computer-Assisted Self-Interviewing (CASI) method. The survey targeted residents of Brno who have at least one child aged 6 to 15, ensuring a representative sample through quota sampling. Participants were divided into an original group (N=114) and a comparison group (N=153). The original group consisted of parents whose children participated in air pollution exposure measurements (see below), thus providing insights from families directly engaged in environmental monitoring efforts. Since participation in this research was voluntary and driven by personal interest, we anticipated a potential bias in this group. To address this, we included a comparison group of parents (N = 153) in the study. The comparison group was sampled from an internet panel in the Czech Republic based on quota sampling criteria, including residence in the city of Brno and having at least one child aged 6–15 years, mirroring the characteristics of the original group. This division allowed for a comparative analysis of transportation choices and the factors influencing them based on exposure awareness and environmental engagement. The survey data thus covered individual demographics, socioeconomics, household characteristics, preferences and attitudes. Descriptive statistics for both groups are presented in Table 1. We also asked parents how important certain aspects of their child's journey to/from school were to them (1 = completely unimportant to 4 = very important). Descriptive statistics are summarised in Table 2.

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of respondents' socioeconomics

Variable	Description	Group	N	Min	Max	Mean	StdDev	%
Age	Age of the respondent	Original	110	32	54	43.73	4.91	
		Comparison	152	28	51	38.60	4.93	
CilldAge	Age of the children	Original	110	6	16	11.7	2.20	
		Comparison	152	5	15	9.69	2.66	
Gender	Gender of respondent, dummy = 1 if female	Original	91					1 = 79.8
		Comparison	114					0 = 16.7
ParentEduc	Education of the respondent, 1 = lower education from primary to Secondary school with maturity exam 2 = Higher education (University)	Original	31					1 = 27.2
		Comparison	80					2 = 70.2
Family Income	Income of family, 1 = Lower income 2 = Middle income 3 = Higher income	Original	15					1 = 13.2
		Comparison	30					2 = 26.3
Family Income	Income of family, 1 = Lower income 2 = Middle income 3 = Higher income	Original	53					3 = 46.5
		Comparison	30					1 = 19.6
Family Income	Income of family, 1 = Lower income 2 = Middle income 3 = Higher income	Original	81					2 = 52.9
		Comparison	40					3 = 26.1

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of respondents' preferences and attitudes

Variable	Description	Group	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std Dev
Aesthetic	Aesthetic reasons (e.g. path through a park, views)	Original	114	1	4	2.13	0.93
		Comparison	153	1	4	2.48	1.14
Comfort	Comfort, convenience	Original	114	1	4	2.66	0.93
		Comparison	153	1	4	3.25	0.83
EnviroImp	Impact on the environment	Original	114	1	4	2.79	0.93
		Comparison	153	1	4	2.68	0.96
FreshAir	Breathing fresh air	Original	114	1	4	3.15	0.92
		Comparison	153	1	4	3.09	0.89
ChildSafety	Child safety	Original	114	1	4	3.70	0.77
		Comparison	153	3	4	3.93	0.25
PhysicAct	Physical activity for children	Original	114	1	4	2.82	1.08
		Comparison	153	1	4	3.08	0.89
Speed	Speed	Original	114	1	4	3.09	0.95
		Comparison	153	1	4	3.41	0.75
TravelCost	Travel Cost	Original	114	1	4	2.26	0.95
		Comparison	153	1	4	2.82	1.03
AirPollution	Perceived air pollution on school route (1 = Definitely no, 4 = Definitely yes)	Original	114	1	4	3.10	0.75
AirPollution	Perceived air pollution on school route (1 = Definitely no, 4 = Definitely yes)	Comparison	153	1	4	2.73	0.81

2.1 Personal air pollution exposure measurement

The participant group included 151 children (ID) from grades 1 to 9 (aged from 6 to 15) across 12 primary schools in Brno. Personal air quality samplers were employed to measure the immediate environmental air quality around each participant, allowing for a detailed assessment of their exposure to pollutants. Participating children wore the samplers for seven consecutive days, one week in the winter and one in the summer, to capture seasonal variability in air pollution exposure. In addition to wearing the devices, children or their parents documented daily activities and modes of transportation in logs, enabling them to link specific activities to air quality levels.

This study utilised personal samplers developed explicitly for this research project to monitor particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) continuously. Personal sampler specifications are detailed in Annex 1. The data samplers were first collocated with a *Grimm* portable laser aerosol spectrometer (Grimm Technologies, Douglasville, GA, USA) for 40 days. Subsequently, calibration regression equations were introduced to achieve maximum measurement accuracy for all data samplers used. Each data collection instance included records with the sampler's ID, timestamp, GPS location, and environmental parameters. The dataset was created based on measurements collected by samplers, which recorded data every 1 minute when actively deployed or every 10 minutes otherwise.

These self-reported details were incorporated into the analysis. All data obtained from the samplers were cleaned, and extreme outliers were trimmed to a maximum value of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This threshold was applied in accordance with the assumptions of the statistical models used. Such extreme values can disproportionately influence statistical parameters such as means and variances, potentially distorting the interpretation of the results. In total, 564 observations exceeding this threshold were removed from the dataset. Only participants with at least 50 valid observations were included in the analysis in each analysed period. The density plot (Figure 1) illustrates the distribution of PM_{2.5} concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for three transportation modes: Car, Walk and Public Transport. The x-axis represents the concentration of PM_{2.5}, while the y-axis shows the probability density, normalised such that the total area under each curve equals 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) for transportation modes

To ensure model validity, assumptions of the primary model were systematically tested. Given the distribution of the dependent variable, it was log-transformed to address skewness. Multicollinearity was assessed using correlation matrices and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis. Residuals were evaluated for normality and homogeneity of variance. Slight deviations from normality were observed for both the dependent variable and residuals, which led to the implementation of alternative models to ensure robustness.

2.2 Statistical Model

A multinomial logit (MNL) model is employed when analysing the determinants of transportation mode choice. The data analysis was conducted in R software, using *nnet* library for data analysis. It models the probability of an individual i choosing a transportation mode j from a set of J discrete options ($j = 1, 2, \dots, J$)

$$P_{ij} = \frac{\exp(U_{ij})}{\sum_{k=1}^J \exp(U_{ik})}$$

where (U_{ij}) represents the utility that the individual i derives from choosing the mode j . The utility function is specified as:

$$U_{ij} = \beta_j X_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Where X_i is a vector of explanatory variables, including socio-economic characteristics, mobility preferences and air pollution concerns, β_j is a vector of coefficients to be estimated for the mode j , representing the relationship between the explanatory variables and the utility of that mode.

In this framework, the logit function for the probability of choosing mode j can also be expressed as:

$$\text{logit}(P(Y = j)) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$$

where j is the mode of commuting, β_n are the coefficients corresponding to each predictor variable X_n .

For evaluation of the air quality, given the repeated measures design (each child has multiple observations over different days and seasons), a mixed-effects linear regression model is used. This model allows for fixed effects (to account for general trends in pollution exposure across predictors) and random effects (to account for variability between individual children and schools).

$$\log (PM_{2.5})_{itj} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Mod_{it} + \beta_5 Season_{it} + u_j + v_i + \varepsilon_{itj}$$

where $PM_{2.5}$ is measured $PM_{2.5}$ level for observation i at time t in school j , Mod is fixed effect for the mode of transport (Walk, Public Transport, Car), $Season$ is fixed effect for the season (e.g., winter, summer), u_j is the random intercept for each school j , accounting for differences in locations or surroundings and also the timing of the campaign, v_i is the random intercept for each individual i , capturing variability in exposure levels due to personal characteristics or behaviour, ε is the residual error term.

To ensure the robustness of the results, the following alternative models were tested: Model without log transformation, where the dependent variable $PM_{2.5}$ is analysed in its original scale, Robust linear model to mitigate the influence of outliers; and Generalised linear mixed model with Gamma distribution for the dependent variable and a log-link function. This specification is well-suited for positively skewed, non-negative data. The data analysis was performed using R software, utilising the following libraries to process and analyse the data: *car*, *lme4*, *robustlmm*, *lmerTest*.

2.3 Alternative routes to school

To further analyse children's school commutes, we examined the actual routes of 47 children who walked or cycled to school, recorded via GPS. These routes were compared with alternative, lower-exposure paths generated using Network Analyst. This analysis allowed us to assess whether children's route choices minimised air pollution exposure and to explore the spatial constraints influencing their mobility decisions.

A polyline layer of roads from the open map database OpenStreetMap served as the primary basis for the analysis. In ArcGIS Pro 3.4, this layer was restricted to the categories: 'footway', 'path', 'pedestrian', 'steps', 'track', 'track_grade1', 'track_grade2', 'track_grade3', 'track_grade4', 'track_grade5', 'cycleway', 'service', 'residential', 'living_street' and, where necessary, was manually edited to include the actual routes children took between home and school as recorded by GPS from personal samplers. Additional input data included point layers for the children's residences and the schools they attended, as well as a polygon layer (20 × 20 m squares) containing values for the average annual PM_{2.5} concentrations (µg/m³), derived from a dispersion study conducted in the city of Brno. This study, developed within the project Monitoring and Measures to Improve Air Quality in the City of Brno, used mathematical modelling data SYMOS97 for the dispersion model to estimate annual and short-term concentrations of selected pollutants, including PM_{2.5} (Masaryk University, 2023).

Each segment in the roads layer was assigned an average annual PM_{2.5} concentration value from the polygon layer based on its location, and this value was then multiplied by the segment length in meters. For each actual home-to-school route travelled by a child, these values were summed across all segments, yielding a "cumulative exposure" value. In the next step, a Network Dataset was created from the roads layer, and the Routes analysis in the Network Analyst extension was used to identify, for each home–school pair, the optimal route with the lowest "cumulative exposure." Thus, rather than travel time or mere distance, the primary criterion was the sum of each segment's distance multiplied by its respective PM_{2.5} concentration value.

3. Results

3.1 Determinants of Children's Mode Transport Choice

We further explored the factors influencing parents' choice of transportation for their children to school in the morning. Respondents (both our participants and people answering the survey) provided information on how their child typically travels from home to school, selecting one or more transportation modes, such as bike/scooter, car, public transport, or walking. Repeated patterns in the data led to a final classification based on the predominant mode of transport, resulting in the following categories: Car only (9%), Active only (a combination of Walking and Bike/Scooter, 42.3%), Public Transport only (16.1%), Combination of Walk and Public Transport, 18.4%), and Mixed mode (various combinations of Car with Public Transport and Walk, 14.2%). Independent variables were grouped into socio-economic factors and mobility preferences, including air pollution concerns, with several models developed within each group to support a comprehensive analysis. The mixed-mode category was excluded from the results table due to its heterogeneity. As it represents a blend of different transport types, it does not allow for clear interpretation within the comparative framework of the analysis.

The study examines the factors influencing the choice of transportation mode based on different groups of variables. For each group, we analysed differences in the likelihood of choosing specific modes of transport, assessing whether the categorisation of respondents into these groups explained variations in their transportation preferences. Active mode was chosen as the reference category. The final models were selected based on statistical significance, interpretability, and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), ensuring they robustly explain the observed variability in mode choice while avoiding overfitting. Models reflect a step-by-step process to better define the factors influencing transportation mode choice (Table 3). Model A includes basic predictors, focusing on key factors that emerged as consistently significant across all transportation modes. Model B was extended to more socio-economic characteristics, while Model C integrates socio-economic factors, adding context to the environmental factors. Model D emphasises a mixed combination of perceptions and socio-economic factors, and Model E represents the full model, incorporating all relevant variables.

Table 3: Determinants of Children's Mode Transport Choice

Variable	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model E
	OR (CI 95 %)	OR (CI 95 %)			
Car					
Intercept	0.1 [0.01, 1.49]	0.01 [0, 0.99]*	0 [0, 0.08]**	0 [0, 0.57]*	0 [0, 1.66]
Group (Comparison)	4.97 [1.72, 14.37]**	2.99 [0.87, 10.27]			4.98 [1, 24.77]
Aesthetic					0.51 [0.26, 0.99]*
Comfort					1.97 [0.82, 4.72]
EnviroImp	0.83 [0.47, 1.46]		0.68 [0.37, 1.23]	0.7 [0.36, 1.34]	0.6 [0.26, 1.38]
FreshAir			1.04 [0.51, 2.1]		2.61 [0.94, 7.23]
ChildSafety					2.71 [0.3, 24.55]
PhysicAct	0.52 [0.31, 0.87]*	0.51 [0.29, 0.89]*		0.52 [0.28, 0.96]*	0.38 [0.18, 0.82]*
Speed	2.15 [1.16, 3.99]*	1.9 [0.95, 3.78]		1.64 [0.84, 3.22]	1.56 [0.71, 3.43]
TravelCost	0.93 [0.55, 1.59]				0.96 [0.51, 1.8]
AirPollution			2.05 [1.01, 4.14]*	1.82 [0.84, 3.97]	1.65 [0.69, 3.94]
ParentAge		1.13 [1, 1.28]*	1.11 [1.01, 1.22]*	1.17 [1.03, 1.32]*	1.16 [1, 1.34]*
ChildAge		0.79 [0.61, 1.03]		0.81 [0.62, 1.06]	0.69 [0.48, 0.99]*
ParentEduc (2)		1.37 [0.42, 4.4]	1.72 [0.61, 4.83]	1.82 [0.58, 5.66]	1.16 [0.29, 4.58]
FamilyIncome (2)		0.8 [0.14, 4.66]		0.71 [0.11, 4.56]	0.51 [0.07, 4]
FamilyIncome (3)		1.25 [0.2, 7.77]		2.11 [0.32, 14.13]	1.28 [0.16, 10.43]
Public Transport					
Intercept	0.16 [0.02, 1.35]	0 [0, 0.23]**	0 [0, 0.04]***	0 [0, 0.13]**	0.01 [0, 10.87]
Group (Comparison)	3.84 [1.66, 8.88]**	1.49 [0.58, 3.81]	0.47 [0.24, 0.93]*		1.83 [0.52, 6.43]
Aesthetic					0.8 [0.41, 1.58]
Comfort					1.41 [0.65, 3.05]
EnviroImp	1.08 [0.66, 1.76]		1.54 [0.81, 2.91]	1.83 [0.97, 3.44]	2.16 [0.87, 5.41]
FreshAir			0.47 [0.24, 0.93]*		0.59 [0.2, 1.72]
ChildSafety					0.45 [0.14, 1.4]
PhysicAct	0.52 [0.33, 0.81]**	0.45 [0.28, 0.72]***		0.23 [0.12, 0.43]***	0.29 [0.14, 0.61]**
Speed	1.36 [0.86, 2.17]	1.63 [0.95, 2.78]		1.39 [0.76, 2.52]	1.1 [0.55, 2.2]
TravelCost	1.5 [0.97, 2.31]				1.84 [1.02, 3.32]*
AirPollution			1.12 [0.64, 1.97]	1.32 [0.68, 2.56]	1.36 [0.63, 2.91]
ParentAge		1.06 [0.96, 1.18]	1.19 [1.09, 1.29]***	1.03 [0.91, 1.16]	1.01 [0.88, 1.15]
ChildAge		1.3 [1.05, 1.6]*		1.56 [1.2, 2.03]**	1.6 [1.2, 2.15]**
ParentEduc (2)		0.94 [0.37, 2.37]	1.12 [0.46, 2.7]	1.12 [0.4, 3.13]	1.05 [0.31, 3.48]
FamilyIncome (2)		0.86 [0.25, 2.95]		2.45 [0.47, 12.89]	2.55 [0.36, 17.99]
FamilyIncome (3)		1.32 [0.36, 4.86]		3.8 [0.7, 20.48]	4.52 [0.58, 35.44]
Combination of Walk and Public Transport					
Intercept	0.21 [0.03, 1.74]	0.07 [0, 2.85]	0.85 [0.03, 26.97]	0.32 [0, 24.97]	1.56 [0, 1316.23]
Group (Comparison)	1.87 [0.83, 4.2]	1.22 [0.48, 3.09]			2.06 [0.64, 6.66]
Aesthetic					0.75 [0.41, 1.37]
Comfort					0.71 [0.38, 1.32]
EnviroImp	0.68 [0.43, 1.08]		1.06 [0.6, 1.87]	0.71 [0.44, 1.14]	0.8 [0.4, 1.59]
FreshAir			0.51 [0.28, 0.93]*		0.7 [0.31, 1.59]
ChildSafety					0.73 [0.24, 2.24]
PhysicAct	0.6 [0.38, 0.94]*	0.53 [0.34, 0.81]**		0.59 [0.35, 1]*	0.79 [0.42, 1.49]
Speed	1.41 [0.88, 2.24]	1.71 [1.03, 2.83]*		1.72 [1.01, 2.93]*	1.78 [0.95, 3.33]
TravelCost	2.13 [1.39, 3.26]***				1.85 [1.12, 3.08]*
AirPollution			0.91 [0.57, 1.47]	0.84 [0.5, 1.4]	0.73 [0.41, 1.31]
ParentAge		1.06 [0.96, 1.16]	1.04 [0.97, 1.12]	1.05 [0.95, 1.16]	1.06 [0.94, 1.18]
ChildAge		1.07 [0.89, 1.29]		1.04 [0.85, 1.27]	1.01 [0.8, 1.27]
ParentEduc (2)		0.55 [0.23, 1.29]	0.6 [0.27, 1.32]	0.65 [0.28, 1.5]	0.48 [0.18, 1.27]
FamilyIncome (2)		0.39 [0.15, 1.01]		0.33 [0.11, 0.95]*	0.33 [0.1, 1.06]
FamilyIncome (3)		0.42 [0.14, 1.26]		0.47 [0.14, 1.54]	0.57 [0.15, 2.15]
AIC	736.66	677.24	654.20	591.29	583.02

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$, OR = Odds Ratio, CI = Confident Interval

The models revealed important insights into the factors influencing transportation mode choices (Car, Public Transport, and Combination of Walk and Public Transport) compared to Active modes. Across all modes, results show that participants are generally less likely to use non-active forms of transportation compared to walking and cycling. Speed emerged as a consistent positive factor influencing the selection of other transport modes, especially car use and the combination of walking and public transport modes, underlining its role as a key determinant in transportation decisions.

For car users, environmental considerations and comfort did not significantly affect car use. In contrast, the perceived importance of physical activity showed a strong and consistent negative effect, indicating that individuals who value physical activity are more inclined toward active travel options. Parental age also showed a positive association with car use in several models, suggesting that older parents may be slightly more likely to drive.

Public transport choices were significantly influenced by family-related factors, particularly the age of children. Having older children was associated with higher odds of using public transport. Similarly, individuals who placed greater importance on physical activity were less likely to choose this mode. Environmental preferences, particularly related to fresh air, showed negative associations with public transport use in some models, possibly reflecting concerns about comfort or hygiene.

Preferences for the combination of walking and public transport were positively associated with both speed and travel cost sensitivity. Travel cost appeared as a significant predictor, indicating that cost-conscious individuals are more likely to select this combined mode. Household income showed a generally negative relationship with the combined mode, suggesting a tendency for lower-income individuals to favour more affordable, active travel options. However, these effects were not always statistically significant. Comfort and aesthetic considerations did not show meaningful associations with this mode, suggesting that practical factors may play a more dominant role in shaping choices. Overall, the final model demonstrated the best fit, as indicated by the lowest AIC value, confirming that the included variables capture important determinants of transportation mode selection.

3.2 Impact of mode of transportation on air pollution exposure

The objective was to determine how the mode of transport affects children's exposure to air pollution during their commute to school. The dataset included measurements from air quality samplers for a total of 151 children, resulting in 10,370 minutes of observations collected during both summer (32.5 %) and winter (67.5 %) seasons. The dependent variable was the concentration of PM_{2.5}, adjusted for outliers to fall within the range of 0–100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for analysis purposes (mean = 20.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, StdDev 17.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Min = 0.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, Max = 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)

Independent variables included the mode of transport – Car (21.6 %), Public Transport (57.1 %), Walk (20.8 %), where Car was chosen as the reference category and Seasons of measurement, Winter (for January, February, March) and summer (for May and June). The effects were controlled for individual school and ID. The results are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Air pollution exposure by mode of transport

	ln PM _{2.5} Model 1		PM _{2.5} Model 2		ln PM _{2.5} Model 3		PM _{2.5} Model 4	
Predictors	Estimates	SE	Estimates	SE	Estimates	SE	Estimates	SE
Intercept	2.89 ***	0.09	22.32 ***	1.67	2.89 ***	0.11	20.06 ***	1.70
Car	-0.62 ***	0.04	-6.08 ***	0.77	-0.60 ***	0.03	0.65 ***	0.03
Public Transport	0.08 **	0.03	2.02 **	0.66	0.11 ***	0.03	1.07 *	0.03
Season Summer	-0.43 ***	0.02	-9.70 ***	0.38	-0.47 ***	0.02	0.62 ***	0.01
Random Effects								
σ^2	0.39		188.22		0.33		0.40	
τ_{00}	0.14 ID_file		70.90 ID_file		0.12 ID_file		0.08 ID_file	
	0.06 School_new		17.07 School_new		0.10 School_new		0.02 School_new	
ICC	0.34		0.32		0.40		0.20	
N	88 ID_file		88 ID_file		88 ID_file		88 ID_file	
	12 School_new		12 School_new		12 School_new		12 School_new	
Observations	10309		10309		10309		10309	
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.166 / 0.445		0.100 / 0.387		0.187 / 0.512		0.150 / 0.320	

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

σ^2 = residual variance, τ_{00} = intercept variance, ICC = intra-class correlation coefficient ICC ($ICC = \tau_{00} / (\tau_{00} + \sigma^2)$)

Figure 2 shows predicted values that represent the expected outcomes of the dependent variable (PM_{2.5} exposure) based on the estimated model coefficients. In this case, the predicted values illustrate how different modes of transport (Car, Public Transport, Walk) are reflected in PM_{2.5} measured concentrations according to four statistical models. The red dots in the figure represent the estimated mean values, and the vertical bars indicate 95% confidence intervals, reflecting the uncertainty in the predictions. The results consistently show that both public transport and walking are associated with higher PM_{2.5} concentrations compared to travelling by car. This trend, observed across all models, suggests that individuals using public transport or walking experience higher pollution levels, while travelling by car probably provides a certain degree of protection from PM_{2.5} exposure.

Figure 2. Predicted values of PM_{2.5} exposure

The primary model (Model 1) analysed the log-transformed PM_{2.5} concentration as the dependent variable, with independent variables including mode of transport, season of measurement, and time of day. Random effects were included to capture variability between groups, specifically at the school level and individual participants (via ID). In addition to the primary model (Model 1), alternative models were employed to test the robustness of the results: a model without log transformation (Model 2), a robust linear model (Model 3), and a generalised linear mixed model with a Gamma distribution (Model 4). These models were employed to verify that the findings of the primary model were consistent and robust under varying analytical assumptions. The non-transformed linear mixed model (Model 2) was retained as part of the robustness checks. However, it exhibited a poorer model fit and did not adequately reflect the distributional characteristics of the dependent variable (PM_{2.5}). The results of the primary model and alternative specifications are presented below.

The results across all four models consistently demonstrate that the mode of transport and season significantly influence children's exposure to air pollution during their commute to school. Car travel is associated with significantly lower PM_{2.5} exposure compared to walking, while public transport shows a modest but consistent increase in exposure relative to walking. These findings are consistent across all statistical approaches and transformations. Each model applies a different statistical framework to validate and ensure the robustness of the findings. The effect sizes remain stable across model specifications, underscoring the reliability and robustness of the observed associations.

Compared to walking, travelling by car or public transport is associated with significantly lower PM_{2.5} exposure, according to the fixed effects of our mixed-effects models. In the main model using a log-transformed outcome (ln PM_{2.5}), car travel was associated with a 62% lower exposure ($\beta = -0.62$, SE = 0.04). In comparison, public transport showed a modest but significant 8% increase ($\beta = 0.08$, SE = 0.03). The model using untransformed PM_{2.5} values produced similar conclusions: car travel was linked to a reduction of 6.08 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (SE = 0.77), whereas public transport resulted in an increase of 2.02 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (SE = 0.66), both relative to walking. These findings were consistent across a robust linear mixed-effects model and a generalised linear mixed model (GLMM) with Gamma distribution, both of which confirmed lower exposure when commuting by car and slightly higher exposure via public transport. Seasonality also played a notable role: summer was associated with a 43–47% reduction in exposure (depending on the model), compared to winter. These findings align with expected seasonal trends in air pollution, likely driven by increased heating-related emissions and reduced atmospheric dispersion during colder months.

However, the fixed effects alone explained only 16.6%–18.7% of the variance, indicating that individual- and school-level factors account for a substantial portion of variability in PM_{2.5} exposure. The conditional R² values ranged from 38.7% to 51.2%, confirming the importance of these random effects in shaping exposure levels. The intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) ranges from 0.20 to 0.40, highlighting the importance of accounting for clustered data.

Figure 3. Predicted values of PM_{2.5} exposure

Source: Masaryk University, 2023; OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025, own data

These findings indicate that children commuting by car experience significantly lower exposure to air pollution compared to those walking, while those using public transport face slightly higher exposure than walkers. Winter conditions further amplify overall exposure levels, likely due to increased emissions from heating and limited atmospheric dispersion. The lower exposure associated with car travel likely reflects protective factors such as closed environments and air filtration systems. In contrast, pedestrians and public transport users are more directly exposed to ambient air pollutants during their commute. The consistency of results across diverse modelling approaches underscores their reliability and robustness.

3.3 Investigation of alternative walking routes to school

A total of 47 children reported walking or cycling to school during the observation period. A comparison of their actual routes (logged using GPS) with the alternative routes generated in Network Analyst (aimed at minimising cumulative exposure) showed that most children behave rationally in spatial terms and generally choose the shortest possible route, which also happens to be optimal in terms of exposure to PM_{2.5} particles. In 30 cases (63.8%), no better route could be identified, largely due to factors inherent in the urban environment—the configuration of buildings and city blocks, the layout of the street network, the presence of sidewalks or cycle paths, etc., which usually offer only limited alternative options.

Figure 4. Model example of actual and alternative routes between home and school

Source: Masaryk University, 2023; OpenStreetMap contributors, 2025, own data

In 17 cases, the analysis did find more suitable routes with lower cumulative exposure; however, these improvements were mostly within just a few percentage points (Table 3). For nearly all children, the alternative route was also shorter (in meters) than the actual route. Only

in two instances did local conditions result in an alternative (better) route that was slightly longer in distance.

Thus, the analysis shows that while there is considerable potential to optimise journeys to school in terms of the number of children affected, the overall improvement in (i.e., reduction of) PM_{2.5} exposure may not always be substantial. This result could be influenced by the available data—20×20 m spatial units for PM_{2.5} concentrations may still be relatively coarse in certain areas, obscuring differences between other potential alternative routes. It is reasonable to assume that greater spatial detail would reveal larger variations in PM_{2.5} values, potentially allowing not only for alternative routes for more children but, more importantly, for a greater reduction in cumulative exposure.

Table 3: Comparison of parameters of children's actual and alternative routes to school (µg/m³)

ID	Actual route			Alternative routes			Differences		
	Length (in meters)	Cumulative exposure (µg/m ³)	Average exposure (µg/m ³)	Length (in m)	Cumulative exposure (µg/m ³)	Average exposure (µg/m ³)	Length (%)	Cumulative exposure (%)	Avg exposure (%)
23095	619.3	7,933.6	12.81	462.2	5,898.8	12.76	-25.4	-25.6	-0.4
23099	1,516.2	20,276.8	13.37	1,316.6	17,368.7	13.19	-13.2	-14.3	-1.4
23135	1,033.3	8,835.8	8.55	937.5	8,039.8	8.58	-9.3	-9.0	0.3
23116	841.6	9,806.3	11.65	848.7	9,736.3	11.47	0.8	-0.7	-1.5
23117	635.8	7,284.8	11.46	567.5	6,380.8	11.25	-10.8	-12.4	-1.9
23009	1,027.7	10,269.7	9.99	1,021.0	10,177.4	9.97	-0.6	-0.9	-0.3
23003	464.2	5,203.8	11.21	421.7	4,617.5	10.95	-9.2	-11.3	-2.3
23005	674.1	9,009.5	13.37	650.9	8,674.4	13.33	-3.4	-3.7	-0.3
23006	894.0	11,915.8	13.33	715.6	8,948.3	12.50	-20.0	-24.9	-6.2
23007	504.2	6,309.4	12.51	486.4	5,805.3	11.94	-3.5	-8.0	-4.6
23070	1,337.9	16,784.1	12.55	1,389.9	15,719.1	11.31	3.9	-6.3	-9.8
23071	535.0	6,098.5	11.40	514.0	5,766.0	11.22	-3.9	-5.5	-1.6
23087	1,050.7	11,342.2	10.80	1,000.0	10,815.6	10.82	-4.8	-4.6	0.2
23033	1,515.0	19,607.6	12.94	1,318.1	15,894.8	12.06	-13.0	-18.9	-6.8
23044	1,433.5	18,544.5	12.94	1,384.4	17,788.3	12.85	-3.4	-4.1	-0.7
23151	321.0	2,372.5	7.39	298.2	2,206.9	7.40	-7.1	-7.0	0.1
23154	733.4	5,327.2	7.26	730.0	5,304.1	7.27	-0.5	-0.4	0.0

Source: Own calculations based on data from personal sensors and air pollution dispersion model (Masaryk University, 2023)

4. Discussion

The findings of this study provide robust evidence on how the mode of transport and seasonal variations significantly influence children's exposure to air pollution during their commutes to school. Across all models, both public transport users and walkers were consistently shown to experience higher exposure to PM_{2.5} concentrations compared to children travelling by car. The results align with existing literature, which highlights the vulnerability of individuals exposed to ambient air pollution in urban environments, particularly during walking or waiting for public transport (Briggs et al., 2008; de Nazelle et al., 2017).

Children commuting by public transport face an increased risk due to longer exposure while waiting at stops or inside vehicles with potentially insufficient ventilation or filtration systems. Similarly, walking and biking are associated with direct exposure to outdoor air pollutants, especially near routes with higher traffic density. These findings are consistent with prior research, which identified walking and public transport as high-exposure modes due to proximity to pollution sources and lack of protective barriers (Zuurbier et al., 2010). In contrast, travelling by car generally offers a controlled environment with built-in air filtration systems that reduce exposure to particulate matter (Xu et al., 2018).

Seasonal effects further strengthen these disparities, with winter consistently associated with higher PM_{2.5} concentrations compared to summer. This seasonal pattern is likely driven by increased emissions from residential heating and reduced pollutant dispersion due to lower temperatures and atmospheric inversions appearing often during colder months, which was also reported by (Cigánková et al., 2021; Song et al., 2022)

The hierarchical data structure used in this study also sheds light on individual and school-level variability in exposure. The intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC), indicated that approximately 20–40% of the variation in PM_{2.5} exposure could be attributed to differences between individuals and schools, highlighting the importance of accounting for clustering in the data through mixed-effects modelling., emphasises the need for localised interventions that consider specific school environments and individual commuting patterns. This aligns with previous research advocating for the integration of local factors into policy measures to effectively address air quality disparities (Brunt et al., 2016).

This research also provides several insights into the determinants of transportation choices, revealing the complex interaction between socio-economic, environmental, and practical factors. The results highlight the influence of socio-economic characteristics, such as age, education, and income, on transportation preferences. Respondents with lower income levels incline more toward the sustainable mode, while the level of education surprisingly had no influence on this choice. These results did not confirm the results of Steg (2005), who emphasised the role of education in fostering environmental consciousness and promoting sustainable behaviour or results Gärling and Schuitema (2007), which emphasised the importance of these determinants in transportation behaviour. The mobility preference models highlighted speed and physical activity as key factors driving the preference for using cars.

Conversely, cost considerations were a significant factor in the Combination of Walk and Public Transport use, emphasising the need to maintain affordability to enhance public transport usage. In one of the models analysed, environmental value emerged as a critical motivator for sustainable choice. These findings align with Gärling and Schuitema (2007), who emphasised the importance of environmental motivations in transportation decisions, as well as (Nordlund & Garvill, 2003) or Moreno-Llamas et al. (2024), who reported a shift toward public transport in response to environmental concerns. However, our study suggested that air pollution concerns minimally influenced transportation decisions. This divergence suggests a growing importance of environmental awareness in urban contexts, reflecting evolving societal attitudes and priorities. These findings highlight the necessity of integrating environmental awareness campaigns with infrastructure improvements to foster a shift toward sustainable modes.

This study has several limitations that should be considered. The exposure data were collected over two short-term periods (winter and summer), which, while capturing seasonal contrasts, do not allow for conclusions about long-term or cumulative exposure. The children wore the sampler for only one week, which can be significantly influenced by the specific meteorological parameters of the period and thus the choice of means of transport. The study focuses on PM_{2.5} exposure only, excluding other potential traffic-related pollutants (e.g., NO₂), and thus may not fully reflect the possible overall exposure. Although the study identifies higher pollution exposure for children using active modes of transport, it does not assess the health benefits of physical activity, making it difficult to evaluate the overall health trade-offs. Study by Tainio et al., (2016) suggests that even under high air pollution scenarios, the positive impact of cycling on overall health surpasses the negative effects of air pollution exposure, making active travel a beneficial choice.

Socio-economic and infrastructural inequalities were only partially captured, which may constrain transport options and disproportionately affect lower-income families. It should also be mentioned that the studied length of potential exposure and the differences in it cannot imply any health conclusions, which are always the result of many different factors.

Furthermore, transport data relied partly on self-reports, which may cause bias. Finally, the study was conducted in one city, limiting the generalisability of results to other urban settings with different mobility patterns and environmental conditions. Future research should address these gaps by including long-term exposure monitoring, a wider range of pollutants, and a stronger focus on health equity and net health outcomes.

4.1 Policy recommendations

Given the model's results, which indicate that children walking or biking to school are generally exposed to higher levels of pollution compared to those traveling by car, these findings highlight the critical need for targeted policy interventions. From a policy perspective, this underscores the importance of improving air quality by designing sustainable transport strategies that

are tailored to the specific geographical, urban, and infrastructural characteristics of the areas surrounding schools, as well as the conditions of the travel routes commonly used by children (Bertazzon and Shahid, 2017; Pantelaki et al., 2024). Promoting sustainable transport and reducing car use are essential for achieving social equity and environmental benefits in urban areas. Low-income households, who often rely on public transport, must not be disadvantaged compared to higher-income groups who predominantly use private cars.

Reducing automobile traffic in urban areas is a critical priority for sustainable city development and emission savings (Carroll et al., 2019). By reducing avoidable car use, cities can create quieter, more liveable environments that enhance the overall well-being of residents. Car-centric urban planning also leads to inefficient land use, as roads, parking areas, and related infrastructure occupy space that could be repurposed for pedestrian zones, bicycle paths, or green areas, which would improve city aesthetics, recreational opportunities, and social interactions (Newman & Kenworthy, 1996).

The conclusions of most studies and international reviews emphasise that the main priority should not be free public transport, which in itself is not sufficient to achieve the goals, but improving the capacity, frequency and overall quality of public transport (Albalate et al., 2024; UITP, 2020). To address these challenges, cities should prioritise investments in public transport, making it more affordable, reliable, and comfortable. Targeted interventions could include upgrading ventilation and filtration systems in public transport vehicles. Policymakers should prioritise and support access to sustainable transportation modes, particularly in areas with high pollution levels, to achieve maximum impact, including cleaner and safer public transport routes.

From our study, speed is shown to be a key factor in the selection of cars and sustainable transport. Policies should aim to reduce travel times for these modes, such as improving the efficiency of public transport systems and the promotion of sustainable modes of transport, such as walking and cycling, which requires significant improvements in pedestrian and cycling infrastructure, such as developing safe, accessible, and interconnected pathways and particularly low-pollution routes to ensure that the health benefits of physical activity are not offset by exposure to harmful air pollutants (Bosch et al., 2020; Jarjour et al., 2013). It also includes improving air quality along public transport routes and pedestrian pathways and incorporating green infrastructure along walking routes, such as trees and hedgerows, to act as barriers against pollutants (e.g. by reducing dust resuspension from roads).

Children, as a particularly vulnerable population group, are disproportionately affected by air pollution due to their developing respiratory and cognitive systems (Alvarez-Pedrerol et al., 2017b). Creating green spaces, planting trees and shrubs, and maintaining clean streets around schools are critical interventions to mitigate these impacts. Well-planned green spaces can act as natural air filters, reducing exposure to nitrogen dioxide or particulate matter, which are prevalent near traffic-heavy areas. For example, studies reveal that green barriers can decrease NO₂ concentrations by 13% and PM_{2.5} levels by 2% in school environments (Redondo Bermúdez et al., 2023) or can reduce PM concentrations by up to 78% in localised areas, with reductions of 40% immediately behind green barriers and further decreases within school

playgrounds (Sheikh et al., 2023). Similarly, urban greenery within 270 meters of schools was shown to be significantly associated with lower indoor concentrations of PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and black carbon, improving indoor air quality for children (Matthaios et al., 2024). Moreover, green spaces near schools can not only improve air quality but can also provide psychological and physical health benefits, such as reducing stress, promoting physical activity, and enhancing cognitive development (Almeida et al., 2022; Roche et al., 2024). In addition to these measures, particular attention should be paid to creating safer and cleaner routes and facilities near schools, such as clean school buses, secure storage for bicycles and scooters, and suitably planned walking paths, which can reduce children's air pollution exposure (Davison et al., 2008).

Promoting multimodal transportation systems that integrate cycling, walking, and public transit through improved infrastructure and incentives can significantly increase speed, convenience and reduce environmental impact. The results showed that environmental factors are not that crucial for the choice of transport. For this reason, equally important are educational campaigns to raise public awareness of the health and environmental consequences of automobile dependency and the benefits of sustainable transportation options, fostering a sense of collective responsibility for adopting pro-environmental mobility behaviour (Moreno-Llamas et al., 2024; Sánchez-García et al., 2021) with the importance of implementing segmentation strategies that consider individual travel attitudes and behaviour (Beirão & Sarsfield Cabral, 2007). Seasonal variations in air pollution exposure further highlight the need for adaptive strategies, such as stricter emission controls during cold months and finer spatial and temporal monitoring of air quality to inform school and community decision-making. Enhancing awareness among parents, schools, and local governments regarding the potential impacts associated with various modes of transport, particularly during winter, can help guide behavioural changes and resource allocation. Implementing these measures can contribute to safer, healthier commuting environments for schoolchildren, thereby reducing the long-term health risks associated with urban air pollution. Moreover, the use of alternative route tracking can serve as a practical tool for local planning, enabling municipalities to identify safer and less polluted pathways (Wang et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

These findings highlight the need for policy and infrastructure improvements that support safe, accessible, and health-promoting commuting environments for all children. Effective interventions can reduce health risks and encourage active commuting by making walking and cycling not only more attractive but also safer and cleaner, which we were able to partially support by analysing possible alternative routes. Importantly, promoting active transport without simultaneously addressing air quality may unintentionally increase health burdens, particularly for children living in high-traffic or polluted urban areas.

Policy recommendations emphasise the importance of considering environmental conditions when promoting active transportation, as evidence confirms its dual role in public health and sustainability. While active travel modes—such as walking and cycling—play a vital role in reducing emissions and promoting physical and mental well-being, their health benefits are dependent on low ambient pollution levels. Urban policies should prioritise the reduction of traffic-related air pollution through the implementation of low-emission zones, green corridors, and traffic-calming measures around schools. Integrated urban planning that connects active transport routes with clean air corridors and invests in high-quality infrastructure (e.g., separated bike lanes, safe crossings, and greenery buffers) can significantly enhance the viability and safety of sustainable mobility options.

Ultimately, this study underlines the complex balance between promoting sustainability and protecting public health. To ensure equitable outcomes, it is crucial that environmental risks are not disproportionately borne by children from families who choose—or are limited to—more sustainable modes of transport. By addressing both mobility behaviour and urban environmental conditions in tandem, policymakers can create healthier, more equitable, and climate-resilient cities for future generations.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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